

**OPEN SCIENCE
HARDWARE GROWTH IN
AFRICA: INSIGHTS FROM A
COMMUNITY FORUM**

2024

This report is the result of contributions from several actors in the open hardware world. The contributions we acknowledge are based on the [CrediT taxonomy](#).
rdware Growth in Africa: Insights from a Community Forum

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Open Science Hardware (OSH) is an emerging movement in Africa with a growing pool of contributors. This report examines the challenges and opportunities associated with this movement while proposing a **theory of change** that outlines strategies to catalyze its development and make it an engine of **African ingenuity through innovative projects that solve specific problems and significantly impact people's lives**.

OSH has considerable potential to provide innovative solutions to local challenges in Africa. The global open science hardware movement, led by the **Gathering for Open Science Hardware (GOSH)** community, aims to democratize access to scientific tools, enabling innovators to tackle the problems that affect their communities. However, in Africa and beyond, the movement faces two major assumptions: many people need to learn what OSH is, and many need to understand its benefits, which is holding back the adoption and development of the movement.

Collective reflections within the **African Open Science Hardware (AfricaOSH) community** have identified strategies for achieving a desired impact, including the development of collective actions led by regional coordinators, the promotion and dissemination of information, OSH education, the development of a participatory research and funding system, a change in mindset, and the connection between organizations working in this field and universities.

Key indicators for assessing the **growth of the movement** in Africa include the accessibility of resources for African innovators, the emergence of students and schools advocating the use of open hardware, and the replicability of African open innovations. This report is the result of discussions involving eight members of the AfricaOSH community, which were facilitated during an online workshop and led to the development of this document.

OSH in Africa has enormous potential for sustainable social innovation. To realize this impact, it is crucial to raise awareness, build capacity, promote partnerships and support locally adapted open hardware solutions. This report aims to guide future efforts to develop Open Science Hardware in Africa, focusing on innovative solutions for local challenges and fostering a collaborative and engaged community.

WHAT IS OPEN SCIENCE HARDWARE?

Science hardware encompasses the tools and machinery we use for scientific endeavors, such as microscopes, environmental sensors, computing devices, and biological reagents. Open Science Hardware refers to science hardware that is open source - or free to use, change, study, or distribute. By opening up science hardware, more people can access the tools we use to do science.

The Open Source Hardware Association (OSHW) defines Open Source Hardware as:

"...hardware whose design is made publicly available so that anyone can study, modify, distribute, make, and sell the design or hardware based on that design."

<https://www.oshwa.org/definition/>

INTRODUCTION

The world's least-developed countries face challenges that require innovative solutions, including new markets, models, and tools. Defining science as the quest for solutions to human problems is both straightforward and practical. This approach, transformed into a profession by the modern architecture of universities and research centers, requires equipment. Indeed, without materials such as instruments, reagents, computers, and other equipment, the production of systematic knowledge is impossible (Dosemagen et al., 2017).

In 2018, the first **African Open Science Hardware Summit was held in Ghana**, marking a significant milestone in the democratization of essential tool design. The event brought together Open Science Hardware enthusiasts and activists, promoted by the Gathering for Open Science Hardware, and served as a platform for sharing knowledge and promoting the movement. Since then, a core group of young people, through the AfricaOSH network, has formed and is working towards common goals for scientific development in Africa. Six years on, it is crucial to reflect on the lessons learned from these efforts and to reconsider our strategies for developing Open Science Hardware for the common good. To this end, **Africitizen has organized a community forum to encourage collective reflection**, understand the evolution of the movement, and define courses of action to improve it. The forum included a dedicated workshop where experts in Open Science Hardware analyzed the challenges associated with its expansion in Africa, and discussed the solutions needed to move it forward.

AFRICA COMMUNITY FORUM FOR OPEN SCIENCE HARDWARE GROWTH

Through the GOSH Community microgrants program, we organized a community forum focused on the general development process of open science hardware in Africa. A workshop that brought together 11 people, including 7 participants, 2 facilitators from GOSH, AfricaOSH communities, and the School of collective intelligence. Through collaborative discussions, this group conducted a reflection marked by two phases: a deconstruction of the problem related to the growth of the open science hardware movement in Africa and a second on the co-construction of a theory of change. Beyond these structural aspects, the workshop was a moment for distributed members to get to know each other and network regarding the actions each is taking, as well as to develop perspectives for common action.

METHODOLOGY

Workshop methodology

This report is the result of a discussion involving eleven members of the African OSH community. Discussions were facilitated during an online workshop, through a two-stage process: deconstructing the problem, then devising a theory of change for the growth of Open Science Hardware.

To enrich the report with more ideas, we distributed a post-workshop form to collect new contributions. This enabled us to collect three new insights. The set of agreed ideas facilitated the writing of this report, which is the start of a series of further in-depth reports focusing on the development of Open Science Hardware in Africa.

Problem deconstruction and theory of change co-design method

Understanding a problem like the growth of OSH in Africa requires an **iterative deconstruction approach to grasp the root causes**. This is why the first step of our methodology involved using the **Ishikawa diagram**, a versatile tool that helps deconstruct problems by identifying and categorizing potential causes. This tool is widely used in various fields; for example, Cahyana (2018) demonstrated its utility in mapping problem causes within information systems. Similarly, in the context of improving teaching quality in universities, it has been used to identify **key areas for quality improvement** by involving teachers and students (Luca et al., 2017).

In the second part, we **co-designed a theory of change (ToC)**. ToC is a planning tool for designing and steering a program that improves a specific problem. The contributions of the participants in this section allowed us to start from a consensus on a desired impact for open hardware, then identify the **outcomes, outputs, and activities** to achieve the desired impact, and also collectively define indicators to measure success. It should be noted that theories of change are applied in **behavior change interventions**, where they help conceptualize and categorize interventions to reveal their theoretical coherence, which improves the design, evaluation, and synthesis of interventions (Gardner et al., 2010). From a **strategic perspective**, the **ToC** allows describing and evaluating the pathways through which an initiative aims to achieve its objectives. The ToC illustrates in detail how and why a desired change is supposed to occur in a specific context, especially in navigating the **complexity of social change** (Sustainable Finance, 2021). The tool involves stakeholders to ensure clarity from the outset, with details and implementation strategies evolving (Mason & Barnes, 2007). Since we are still in the **open science field**, use cases show that the ToC has been used to plan, manage, and evaluate **research-related interventions**, particularly in areas such as agriculture in service of nutrition and health (Mayne & Johnson, 2015).

OPEN SCIENCE HARDWARE AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN AFRICA

Open Science Hardware (OSH) is an emerging concept in Africa, applied unstructured and perceived differently across the continent. This situation is not unique to Africa, as the global movement represents a new paradigm. More and more people worldwide are developing and using open scientific hardware. However, a coherent, self-organized community must emerge, capable of raising its profile and driving social change in institutions to increase its adoption (GOSH, 2016).

OSH is defined as a set of laboratory instruments using open-source materials to promote epistemic (improving knowledge of nature) and normative (improving society) ideals, with an emphasis on the importance of technology (Kera, 2017). At this stage in its evolution, OSH can be seen as a movement of actors striving to make scientific practice accessible and useful to society, with a commitment to sustainability, thus facilitating the design and distribution of materials on a global scale. This movement is characterized by a dynamic of decentralization in the mobilization and organization of efforts across different regions and global communities, aiming to emerge common goods for a science that responds to our current challenges. Design technologies that can be easily and economically used by local communities, from readily available resources, to meet their needs (The Case for Open Source Appropriate Technology, s. d.).

CHALLENGES IN DEVELOPING THE OSH MOVEMENT IN AFRICA

The development of movements such as Open Science Hardware represents a **change in the organizational structure of society, complexified by social and behavioral dynamics**. Addressing long-term social and economic challenges via technology requires the design of new and emerging systems (Mohideen & Evans, 2015). Such a movement, especially with an international scope, needs to adapt to the varied dynamics and rhythms of different communities. As Mcneely (2003) points out, cultural factors play a crucial role in the adoption of new technologies. Indeed, diverse cultural perceptions and values can **influence how technologies are accepted and integrated into everyday life**. It is therefore **essential to take these cultural differences** into account to ensure successful technology transfer and implementation. This highlights the need to **consider the subtleties that define the dynamics of the OSH movement in Africa**, a region where researchers face many challenges, including technical constraints, environmental conditions, and cultural barriers that can compromise successful technology implementation. Understanding these challenges is crucial to avoiding past mistakes and adapting technology appropriately to different contexts (Brewer et al., 2006).

To better support scientists and innovators, it is essential to have a deep understanding of the realities of these change agents. That's why we've undertaken a collaborative deconstruction of the problem: **the slow growth of the OSH movement in Africa**.

Leadership in the open science hardware movement

The community forum participants analyzed in depth the fundamental causes of the slow development of Open Science Hardware. One of the main problems identified is the **lack of leadership, manifested in the absence of a clear agenda and insufficient definition of the societal problems the movement seeks to solve**. Participants emphasized that issues related to access to water and food should be prioritized.

They also noted the absence of an African board dedicated to organizing initiatives, underlining the need to strengthen the administration established after the African Open Science Hardware summit in Ghana to improve its influence and initiative. A concrete example of an initiative would be to better value student projects at the university, which are currently undervalued.

Raising awareness of Open Science Hardware

The lack of direction and vision in Africa regarding open science hardware manifests itself in several ways. This reveals a second cause hindering the development of the movement: the general lack of knowledge about Open Science hardware. In the words of one participant: "People don't see the benefits of OSH". This situation calls for better means of communication to promote the movement, including a stronger online presence and, of course, efforts in the field. Identifying and disseminating information is essential to generate greater interest in Open Science Hardware. In addition, there is a lack of mobilization of local communities around specific projects and a lack of collaboration, often due to fear among community members of sharing their ideas for fear of having them stolen (due to a low culture of innovation and entrepreneurship).

There is also a lack of systems to identify and promote people who are making significant achievements. Encouraging recognition is therefore essential to developing a sense of belonging.

Inadequate resources for experimentation

Lack of resources for experimentation is a major obstacle, not least because of the **high costs associated with shipping tools to Africa**. Added to this are problems of access to electricity and the Internet in most countries, as well as a tendency to replicate projects from other regions without adapting solutions to the specific local problems that should fuel the design of open hardware for transformative research projects. These difficulties are exacerbated by a lack of funding for initiatives aimed at raising funds to support open hardware innovators and manufacturers in Africa. Participants also highlighted specific challenges, such as **difficulties in transferring funds to Africa** and inefficiencies or complications encountered when using participatory financing methods.

THEORY OF CHANGE FOR OPEN HARDWARE GROWTH IN AFRICA

To formulate the requirements of the solution(s) we seek to advance open hardware in Africa, we conducted a Theory of Change (ToC) development with contributions from community forum participants. Thus, a targeted impact for the Open Science Hardware movement in Africa over the long term hinges on a movement with a clear goal.

To better support scientists and innovators, it is essential to have a deep understanding of the realities of these change agents. That's why we've undertaken a collaborative deconstruction of the problem: the slow growth of the OSH movement in Africa.

Impact

A movement that develops open hardware to catalyze African ingenuity, implementing innovative projects that solve specific problems and have a significant impact on people's lives.

The formulation of an impact intimately linked to public problems and social impact can be explained by the realities of the context. Indeed, the purpose of a movement like OSH, technological change, does not occur in isolation. It is a change that is profoundly influenced by societal contexts and involves the adaptation of technology in various fields (MacKenzie & Wajcman, 1987).

Outcomes

- O1: Lead a collective action driven by regional coordinators (04) for hardware science in East Africa, West Africa, Central Africa, and South Africa, to promote diversity of approaches.
- O2: Promote and disseminate information to increase knowledge of Open Science Hardware.
- O3: Integrate Open Science Hardware education into school curricula, connecting the movement to schools and young people.
- O4: Set up a participatory funding system for open hardware makers in Africa.
- O5: Encourage a change of mindset in open hardware design, oriented towards solving local community problems.
- O6: Establish connections between open-source hardware organizations and universities.

Assumptions

To develop solutions that will help us achieve our goals, it's crucial to consider the assumptions associated with the movement in Africa. This will enable us to design objective responses that are beyond these assumptions. Two major ideas have been identified:

- **Many people don't know what open hardware is.**
- **Many don't understand the benefits of open hardware.**

These two ideas reveal that the actions that can lead us to the desired impact for the movement should include: first, introducing people to the movement, then explaining how it works, and finally highlighting its benefits.

Success indicators

The achievement of the results identified above can be measured using specific indicators such as :

1. **Accessibility of resources by African innovators:** This can be measured by the number of open hardware prototypes used by innovators and researchers.
 2. **Emergence of students and schools advocating the use of open hardware:** Success here can be measured by the number of peer ambassadors.
- **Replicability of African open innovations across the continent to solve local problems:** This measure can be monitored by an innovation tracking system.

Strategic directions for change

To achieve a transformative impact with the OSH movement in the pursuit of sustainable social innovation, we can implement the following core strategies:

- Develop monitoring of African initiatives: Set up a database of scientific initiatives using open hardware in Africa.
- Use technology to effectively promote open hardware.
- Mobilize more funding for open hardware manufacturers in Africa.
- Integrate the use of open hardware in universities.
- Strengthen open hardware communities in Africa, to foster collaboration.

Outputs and key activities

The contributions to the collective reflections help identify activities to be developed to bring about a change in the development of the Open Science Hardware movement in Africa. We are therefore elaborating a series of recommendations by developing outputs and activities arising from the identified outcomes.

- **O1: Develop a regional development plan for Open Science Hardware across Africa**
 - Develop an ongoing systematic census of local OSH players across different regions
 - Conduct studies to understand profiles and their professional situations
 - Organize brainstorming sessions to identify synergies of action for the emergence/growth of OSH ecosystems by region.
 - Strengthening policies, improving collaboration and funding, creating new businesses
- **O2: Produce more OSH content:**
 - Produce video and document content to popularize OSH
 - Design a course on the subject: how to start OSH in Africa
 - Produce communication tools for social networks to take advantage of growing connectivity in Africa
 - Use a group of representatives as ambassadors to disseminate outreach content.
 - Create common thinking about how to use this software, create very well-known platforms to store this data that everyone knows about (not like GitHub and other similar platforms), and promote different workshops and exhibitions about this software and the platform by encouraging people to do them and integrating these software devices with potential individuals (financial+ production). One participant on this point said that a platform that is not GitHub is needed. This questioned whether popular tools like GitHub are complicated to use. So, it's important to rethink solutions for developing online interaction makers in OSH. For example, through WhatsApp APIs, develop more functionality to extend the WhatsApp group to the African OSH community.

- **O3: The Open Science Hardware integration strategy is up and running:**
 - Identify academic profiles that can adopt OSH in their work
 - Identify prototype solutions adapted to pedagogical and research needs
 - Analyze the right strategy for acquiring prototypes and using them in courses at both secondary and higher education levels
 - Evaluate the impact of the use of these tools in improving the quality of education
 - Use evaluation results to advocate the integration of OSH into educational programs.

- **O4: Have a financing strategy for OSH development**
 - Bring the problem of financing activities back to the heart of discussions
 - Identify activities around OSH with high-added value that could attract sources of investment.
 - Identify collaborations between researchers in developed countries and those in Africa in search of funding.

- **O5: Local needs are integrated into OSH promotion strategies**
 - Identify the major public problems that OSH can help solve
 - Identify synergies of action between non-scientists and scientists in the design of Open Hardware prototypes.
 - Strengthen collaboration between Open Hardware innovators and scientists to create synergies that benefit both parties.

- **O6: Develop institutional partnerships between OSH organizations and universities.**
 - Many universities in Africa have training programs that lack a practical component. Establishing partnerships with these would enable OSH to provide the practical side of training.
 - Identify these training courses in African universities, as well as student associations representing young people.
 - Develop partnership strategies to introduce prototypes of open hardware solutions that can be used for practical work.
 - Makerspaces can also be created in different areas of the institution.

CONCLUSION

The development of Open Science Hardware in Africa has got off to a timid start, but it has a great deal of potential. These potentials enable the successful implementation of open hardware projects, responding to local challenges and promoting innovative solutions. To achieve this, ongoing efforts to raise awareness and understanding of open hardware principles among researchers and educators need to be reinforced. This includes building the capacity of local innovators to design, build and document open hardware, fostering partnerships and collaborations between African OSH initiatives and global OSH networks, increasing public awareness and support for open hardware initiatives and citizen science projects, and encouraging the emergence of locally adapted and context-specific open hardware solutions to meet African needs.

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